

Comment on “A sensory system for mating in octopus”

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Abstract

A recent research article by Villar *et al.* (1) proposes that mating behavior in octopuses is guided by contact-mediated chemosensation involving progesterone, which is described as a “conserved ovarian hormone.” Although this work is remarkable from the neurobiology, behavior, receptor evolution, and structural biology perspectives, its interpretation raises major questions regarding steroid biology in invertebrates, and more specifically in mollusks.

Main text

The central claim of the article by Villar *et al.* (that progesterone act as an endogenous physiological signal for reproduction) rests on the implicit idea that vertebrate-type short-chain steroids are synthesized and utilized in cephalopods in a manner comparable to that observed in vertebrates, as also suggested by some earlier studies (2, 3). However, this hypothesis is strongly challenged by a converging body of biochemical, genomic, and evolutionary data accumulated over many years.

First, available biochemical analyses do not support the existence of vertebrate-type steroids as endogenous regulators in the octopus. Several highly specific mass spectrometry approaches failed to detect steroids such as cortisol, corticosterone, or estradiol in the hemolymph of octopus, whether under control conditions or under stress conditions (4). Progesterone has previously been found in the soft tissue of a wide variety of mollusks, including octopus (collected in (5)). In most

of these studies, however, the apparent presence of progesterone was measured by immunoassay, which is well-known not to be suitable for reliably detecting steroids in tissues/tissue extracts. Some of the studies also quantified progesterone with mass spectrometry in mussels (6, 7) and octopus (8), yet these findings must be interpreted cautiously. Some of us have demonstrated that snails exposed to [³H]-progesterone for 8 hours, and mussels exposed for 24 hours, readily absorbed the steroid from the exposure water and were able to retain it for prolonged periods (even for weeks) (5, 9). Following exposure to waterborne [³H]-progesterone, progesterone-derived radioactivity in tissue extracts was associated with water-soluble, free, and esterified fractions of the soft tissues (5, 9). In mussels, further analyses revealed that intact progesterone could not be detected in these fractions; instead, two metabolites, 5 α -pregnane-3 β ,20 β -diol and 3 β -hydroxy-5 α -pregnan-20-one, were definitively identified, suggesting 3-ketosteroid reductase activities on the absorbed progesterone, similar to those that are carried out by some HSD3B paralogs in mammals (10). The findings obtained in snails also tentatively suggested a similar metabolic pathway, as the progesterone-derived radioactivity eluted as two peaks consistent with the 5 α -reduced steroids identified in the blue mussel. These observations raise an important question: if progesterone is rapidly metabolized by mollusks, how should reports of progesterone itself in molluscan tissues be interpreted? This issue is particularly relevant when examining the supplementary data in the Villar *et al.* study. According to their Table S1, among the three replicates coming from ovary tissue, there is only one (sample 2) for which the two progesterone multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) fragments were found. The same situation can be observed in the oviduct, where the signal-to-noise ratios are even worse, where only sample 1 contains putative progesterone fragments. The only tissue where MRM fragments were found consistently in all three sample was the skin, which would be very consistent with an exogenous contamination by external progesterone. Additionally, it is also important to notice that, with one exception (sample 2 Ovary), the analyses in the tissue samples were performed close to the detection limit. This is also suggested by the signal-to-noise values ranging between 3.1 and 6.5.

Second, from a genomic and evolutionary perspective, it is clear that the canonical pathway of vertebrate steroid biosynthesis is not conserved in mollusks. In vertebrates, two generic types of reaction are involved in steroidogenesis. The first type - in which two hydrogen atoms can be either inserted or removed (oxidoreductase reactions) - is relatively simple and occurs for example at the

stage of transformation of pregnenolone to progesterone (catalyzed in vertebrates by the enzyme 3 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase [3 β -HSD]). Oxidoreductase reactions are relatively simple, widely distributed, and can act on a variety of substrates (i.e. not just steroids, or not only steroids with a cleaved side-chain) (10). Although the evidence for their occurrence in mollusks is strong, evidence that these reactions are part of a steroid biosynthetic pathway which is equivalent to that of vertebrates is circumstantial due to the involvement of HSDs in other metabolic pathways (11). Moreover, the annotation of oxidoreductases is often based on homologies with vertebrate proteins, which can lead to misleading functional interpretations. While the Villar *et al.* paper does not provide the predicted protein sequences on which they could have based the annotation of their RNA-seq data, it is possible to clarify this issue using *Octopus* sequences available in Genbank. Updating a previously published HSD3B tree ((12), Figure S6), and taking into account a broader set of outgroup sequences (13), we can unambiguously confirm that molluscan HSD3B sequences are nested in a group that is paralogous to the vertebrate HSD3B acting on side-chain cleaved steroids. They are equally related to those than to the HSD3B7 enzymes acting in the bile acid synthesis pathway, which catalyze a similar reaction but on steroids with a cleaved side chain (**Fig. 1**).

The second type of reaction - in which oxygen atoms are inserted - is relatively complex and involves enzymes that belong to the Cytochrome P450 family (CYP). One such reaction is the cleavage of the cholesterol side chain by CYP11A1, which generates pregnenolone, a precursor of progesterone. Comparative analyses show that some of the essential CYP components, including CYP11A and CYP19A, are absent in protostomes, including mollusks (11, 12, 14-17). In particular, CYP11A is not present in the genome and/or neuronal transcriptome of *Octopus bimaculoides* (18), *Aplysia californica* (19), *Lymnaea stagnalis* (20, 21), and *Biomphalaria glabrata* (22). More generally, some of us have demonstrated that steroidogenesis pathways have evolved independently in different animal lineages, and there is no evidence to suggest that the vertebrate pathway is present in the octopus (12).

Taken together, the available evidence – detection of progesterone/progesterone-like compounds in tissues, expression of individual enzymes capable of steroid metabolism, and behavioral responses to exogenous progesterone – does not support the conclusion that progesterone functions

as an endogenous reproductive signal in octopus. Importantly, none of these considerations diminish the significance of the findings reported by the Villar *et al.* study, as the authors convincingly demonstrate that exogenous progesterone triggers a response in the hectocotylus and can induce exploratory behaviors associated with mating. However, the ability of a sensory system to respond to an exogenous molecule does not constitute proof that this molecule is an endogenous physiological signal. Bisphenol A, for example, has a specific and conserved effect in humans and several vertebrates, acting via multiple receptors, and yet this effect is purely pharmacological, as bisphenol A is not produced in vertebrates since it is a man-made industrial pollutant. This clearly demonstrates that chemosensory systems, particularly in aquatic organisms, can recognize a wide range of hydrophobic compounds sharing structural properties. This possibility is further supported by the receptor pharmacology reported by the Villar *et al.* article. According to their Table S3, the CR888 receptor also responds to 7α -hydroxy-4-cholesten-3-one, which is the actual substrate for the vertebrate bile-salt metabolizing HSD3B.

An alternative interpretation, fully compatible with the behavioral and neurobiological observations reported by Villar *et al.*, is that octopus use an endogenous lipophilic signal produced by reproductive tissues that remains chemically unidentified. Such a molecule could share structural and physicochemical properties with progesterone and therefore activate the same receptor system while being clearly distinct from progesterone itself. Under this scenario, progesterone would serve as an effective experimental analog rather than the physiological ligand. This hypothesis reconciles the receptor activation data with the current lack of convincing evidence for endogenous progesterone biosynthesis in mollusks. Thus, although the study by Villar *et al.* provides compelling evidence for a mating-related chemosensory pathway in octopus, the available data do not demonstrate that progesterone is the endogenous ligand mediating this response. Identifying the endogenous signal, establishing its biosynthetic pathway, and linking its production to receptor activation and reproductive behavior will be essential next steps, as repeatedly emphasized in critical reviews of vertebrate-type steroid signaling in mollusks (11, 14, 23, 24). More broadly, describing progesterone as a “conserved hormone” across metazoans carry the risks of perpetuating a vertebrate-centric view of endocrinology, despite growing evidence that endocrine systems evolved independently in different animal lineages with distinct ligands, receptors, and metabolic pathways (12).

References

1. P. S. Villar *et al.*, A sensory system for mating in octopus. *Science* **392**, 96-101 (2026).
2. E. De Lisa, M. Paolucci, A. Di Cosmo, Conservative nature of oestradiol signalling pathways in the brain lobes of octopus vulgaris involved in reproduction, learning and motor coordination. *J Neuroendocrinol* **24**, 275-284 (2012).
3. A. D'Aniello *et al.*, Occurrence of sex steroid hormones and their binding proteins in *Octopus vulgaris* lam. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* **227**, 782-788 (1996).
4. B. H. Maskrey *et al.*, Studies on cortisol, corticosterone, and 17beta-estradiol indicate these steroids have no role in stress or reproduction in the common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*). *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* **328**, E105-E115 (2025).
5. T. I. Schwarz, I. Katsiadaki, B. H. Maskrey, A. P. Scott, Uptake and metabolism of water-borne progesterone by the mussel, *Mytilus* spp. (Mollusca). *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol* **178**, 13-21 (2018).
6. M. A. Reishenriques, J. Coimbra, Variations in the Levels of Progesterone in *Mytilus edulis* during the Annual Reproductive-Cycle. *Comp Biochem Phys A* **95**, 343-348 (1990).
7. M. H. Devier, P. Labadie, A. Togola, H. Budzinski, Simple methodology coupling microwave-assisted extraction to SPE/GC/MS for the analysis of natural steroids in biological tissues: application to the monitoring of endogenous steroids in marine mussels *Mytilus* sp. *Anal Chim Acta* **657**, 28-35 (2010).
8. Z. Y. Wang, M. R. Pergande, C. W. Ragsdale, S. M. Cologna, Steroid hormones of the octopus self-destruct system. *Curr Biol* **32**, 2572-2579.e4 (2022).
9. I. Fodor *et al.*, Studies on a widely-recognized snail model species (*Lymnaea stagnalis*) provide further evidence that vertebrate steroids do not have a hormonal role in the reproduction of mollusks. *Front Endocrinol* **13**, 981564 (2022).
10. J. Simard *et al.*, Molecular biology of the 3beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase/delta5-delta4 isomerase gene family. *Endocr Rev* **26**, 525-582 (2005).
11. I. Fodor, P. Urban, A. P. Scott, Z. Pirger, A critical evaluation of some of the recent so-called 'evidence' for the involvement of vertebrate-type sex steroids in the reproduction of mollusks. *Mol Cell Endocrinol* **516**, 110949 (2020).
12. G. V. Markov *et al.*, Independent elaboration of steroid hormone signaling pathways in metazoans. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **106**, 11913-11918 (2009).
13. E. Desmond, S. Gribaldo, Phylogenomics of sterol synthesis: insights into the origin, evolution, and diversity of a key eukaryotic feature. *Genome Biol Evol* **1**, 364-381 (2009).
14. A. P. Scott, Do mollusks use vertebrate sex steroids as reproductive hormones? Part I. Critical appraisal of the evidence for the presence, biosynthesis and uptake of steroids. *Steroids* **77**, 1450-1468 (2012).
15. T. Balbi, C. Ciacci, L. Canesi, Estrogenic compounds as exogenous modulators of physiological functions in molluscs: Signaling pathways and biological responses. *Comp Biochem Physiol C Toxicol Pharmacol* **222**, 135-144 (2019).
16. T. Horiguchi, Y. Ohta, A critical review of sex steroid hormones and the induction mechanisms of imposex in gastropod mollusks. In: Saber Saleuddin ABL, Orchard I, editors. *Advances in invertebrate (Neuro)Endocrinology*, 1st edition. Boca Raton: Apple Academic Press (2020).
17. G. V. Markov *et al.*, Origin of an ancient hormone/receptor couple revealed by resurrection of an ancestral estrogen. *Sci Adv* **3**, e1601778 (2017).
18. C. B. Albertin *et al.*, The octopus genome and the evolution of cephalopod neural and morphological novelties. *Nature* **524**, 220-224 (2015).
19. L. L. Moroz *et al.*, Neuronal transcriptome of Aplysia: neuronal compartments and circuitry. *Cell* **127**, 1453-1467 (2006).
20. J. M. Koene *et al.*, The genome of the simultaneously hermaphroditic snail *Lymnaea stagnalis* reveals an evolutionary expansion of FMRFamide-like receptors. *Sci Rep* **14**, 29213 (2024).
21. I. Fodor, J. M. Koene, Z. Pirger, Neuronal Transcriptome Analysis of a Widely Recognised Molluscan Model Organism Highlights the Absence of Key Proteins Involved in the De Novo Synthesis and Receptor-Mediation of Sex Steroids in Vertebrates. *Malacologia* **64**, 69-77 (2021).
22. C. M. Adema *et al.*, Whole genome analysis of a schistosomiasis-transmitting freshwater snail. *Nature Commun* **8**, 15451 (2017).
23. A. P. Scott, Do mollusks use vertebrate sex steroids as reproductive hormones? II. Critical review of the evidence that steroids have biological effects. *Steroids* **78**, 268-281 (2013).

24. K. Panagiotidis, T. H. Miller, O. V. Martin, A. Baynes, Mapping molluscan endocrinology: a systematic and critical appraisal. *Biol Rev Camb Philos Soc* **101**, 970-1002 (2026).

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Figure legend

Fig. 1. A maximum-likelihood phylogeny of HSD3B sequences. ALRT branch support value above 0.97 are indicated. Vertebrate steroidogenic HSD3B acting on steroids without a side chain like pregnenolone, are highlighted in blue. Molluscan sequences are highlighted in red. The yellow highlight indicates a clade of sequences that may carry HSD3B activities, but probably originally on steroids with a lateral side-chain, like 7α -hydroxycholesterol in vertebrate bile acid synthesis.

Fig. 1.

